

Determinants & Impact of Sovereign Credit Ratings

Farhana Akter¹, Min Su², Ophelia Amankwah³

¹College of Economics and Management, Taiyuan University of Technology, China

Accepted Feb 03,2021

Published Jan 07,2021

*Corresponding Author:

Farhana akter,

farhanakhanlive19@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4515670>

Pages: 43-58

Funding: Not funded.

Distributed under
Creative Commons CC BY 4.0

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article (APA):

Farhana Akter, Min Su, & Ophelia Amankwah (2021). Determinants & Impact of Sovereign Credit Ratings. *North American Academic Research*, 4(2), 43-58. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4515670>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to investigate the factors that determine credit ratings provided by the top three credit rating agencies: Fitch Rating, Moody's, Standards and Poor. Key component analysis is used to determine the common factors affecting these components. A systematic analysis is used to determine the effect of the changes involved in these factors. Of the many variables used, the set of explanatory variables chosen in this study is very important in describing credit ratings. That said, six variables appear to be most relevant in determining a country's credit rating. The results show that sovereignty ratings are primarily affected by per capita income, government income, real exchange rate fluctuations, inflation and debt history. The study also highlighted the importance of corruption as measured by Transparency International's Corruption Awareness Index, which appears to be indicative of the country's economic growth and good governance.

Keywords: CREDIT RATINGS, SOVEREIGN CREDIT RATINGS, STANDARDS & POOR'S, PANEL DATA, RANDOM DATA.

1. Introduction

This article looks at the factors that work to determine the level of government bonds. To that end, we used page examples to compile data on population and capacity data from 23 developed and developing countries, as well as from 2011 & 2020 for Standard & Poor's and Moody's provided. To mitigate this situation, we want to assess the correct level of the two companies. This can be done by changing the system and the order level. The book is organized as follows: How clean are the standards for sovereignty levels? Also, how much does rating affect the cost of national borrowing? To find these questions, we provide a second method, a pre-structured assessment of the factors and outcomes of the credit score assigned by S. Group Channeling is a

provider and an investor's trend and bidding. The sovereign credit rating is a measure of the willingness to pay for government welfare and debtor's principal and welfare (services). Exchange rates vary from country to country. So, first of all, consider the king's risk, so the level of foreign debt is lower than the level of the mortgage loan. Of course, the government can use local debt to pay taxes or generate income. On the other hand, officials must own foreign currency to repay foreign debts. In addition, the government may prevent other companies from repaying foreign debts to non-residents. Assign you based on the variability and qualitative changes that the planning company considers trustworthy. The rate of change encompasses a wide range of economic and socio-economic processes, and in many cases the political and predictive aspects of the degree of improvement are analyzed. Since the state is represented as a state, sovereign deposits are a measure of value. Agencies allow companies to give creditors a credit rating based on their credit score. It is taken from Fitch Ratings, a management company that collects data from various government channels (mainly the International Monetary Fund). The data is divided into eight classification used in Fitch's sovereign rating methodology: economy, money and banking, government finance, exchange rate and competitiveness, trade openness, external assets and liabilities, income, demographics.

We were also included in the empirical analysis review, which was mentioned as a key element by the Institute of Research and Development. Government debt and government debt information (i.e. 12 creditors and paris waves) were collected by World Bank's Global Development Finance (2003) and analyzed using the following criteria: Correct or improve debt to government creditors. At least once in the history of the assigned group, a country without an initial seal record is assigned. According to the theory of credit risk sovereignty, the literature emphasizes two topics. The first shows the ability of the state to pay off its debts in a timely manner. Second, focus on your willingness to pay off your debts. This document focuses on the latest indicators. This important indicator plays an important role in international capital markets in many ways. Credit rating generally affects the interest rate paid by countries receiving credit in international financial markets. Over time, expert assistance has been needed to support a firm's financing, risk management, and investment decisions. Its significance led to this adjustment i. for emerging economies, sovereign ratings are important because they give these countries and the private sector a better position in foreign direct investment and access to global financial markets. Local organizations contribute to better knowledge of this article credit rating. This study could ultimately provide investors and governments with information on the impact of their ability to meet their debt obligations on ratings. Future credit investors will find this study useful.

2.Literature Review

The potential determinants of sovereign debt-servicing difficulties, default and sovereign ratings selected by different empirical models were derived from theoretical models on sovereign default, previous empirical evidence or rating agency reports. Collecting all of these sources, past or present corporate data, suggests that national credit risk can be captured with minor economic and political changes. These changes are not very

different from study and study. Table 1 lists several important factors used in documentation that influence the validity of sovereignty at the national level. There are several types of operating systems that can be used to handle debt and public debt in two ways. The first raises the question of why the debtor should pay off his debt. The reason debtors have to pay off their debts is that they cannot get help from the bankruptcy or enforcement of Eaton and Gersovitz. (1981). Designed to maintain a good reputation and maintain a future credit market, it is an incentive for countries to be rewarded for it. The basis for this result is that states have decided to respect their debts if the future borrowing ratio does not exceed the short-term profit of high consumption. The (cost carrier) decides to pay if a pending trade deal is proposed. It is an opportunity for future product launches and borrowing. In addition to economic, political, and legal constraints, you can rent a small country. For example, Aylward and Thorne (1998) and Peter (2002) questions provide a summary of all changes. That test in the study is most important because the state is not just a place to live. The main purpose of this book is to carefully analyze the factors that determinants of sovereign ratings, that is a text review focusing on key themes. In order to carefully review the first-level paid books, people interested in reading should consider, such as Eaton and Fernandez (1995) and Obstfeld and Rogoff (1996). Why should the country repay its foreign debt? Kremer and Mehta (2000) argue that although the government pays foreigners, they usually pay higher prices. In fact, international standards are usually lower than domestic standards (see, for example, Trevino and Thomas, 2001).

However, states can pay off their foreign debt for three reasons. First of all, foreign investors can still hold foreign currency if the state does not pay off their debt. Second, the country may not be able to access foreign loans in the future. Finally foreign debt settlement can eventually have a negative impact on international trade (see e.g. Gibson and Sundaresan, 2001; Rose, 2002). Under this framework, countries take into account the cost and benefit of repayment (Haque et al., 1996). Thus, the special case is a function of incremental change that incentivizes the country and the work of reduced change that increases the initial rate. The starting number is usually a credit card. The main economic changes discussed in this book are: income per capita gross domestic product (GDP), inflation, economic growth, foreign debt and GDP growth, real changes and reports support. The sustainability due to short- or long-term fluctuations in frequency will determine the likelihood of default. However, according to Roubini (2000), it is not always easy to distinguish between a stopover and a waterfall, but many lines allow us to consider local support. This brochure provides an overview of current account balance, inflation, exchange rate, monetary policy, foreign debt, public debt, gross domestic product (GDP), short- and long-term results, and international income ... many economic changes often This happens twice because it affects the value of a nation's leverage opportunity as well as its debt serviceability. There is no information on community finance education as the industry has begun to evaluate many cities. due to short- or long-term fluctuations in frequency will determine the likelihood of default. However, according to Roubini (2000), it is not always easy to distinguish between a stopover and a waterfall, but many lines allow us to consider local support. This brochure provides an overview of current account balance, inflation, exchange

rate, monetary policy, foreign debt, public debt, gross domestic product (GDP), short- and long-term results, and international income many economic changes often. This happens twice because it affects the value of a nation's leverage opportunity as well as its debt serviceability. There is no information on community finance education as the industry has begun to evaluate many cities. The earliest examples of this literature are Feder and Uy (1985), Cosset and Roy (1991) and Lee (1993), which are based on data from two international publications: Euromoney and/or Institutional Investor to analyze sovereign risk rankings. Is. Haque et al. (1996) provided empirical evidence that economic variables can explain the volatility of domestic credit ratings provided by these two magazines and the Economic Intelligence Bureau. In a subsequent paper, Haque et al. (1998) based on the study of Lee (1993) and found that economic variables have a greater impact on country rankings than political variables. Ratio of short-term foreign debt to reserves. According to the research of Cantor & Packer (1996), six financial variables play an important role in determining the sovereign credit rating issued by Standard & Poor's and Moody's. These variables are per capita income, real GDP growth, inflation, investment GDP, unemployment, external debt, budget balance and basic history. In contrast, the analysis of 49 countries/regions using several regression methods did not show any systematic relationship between the degree and the budget deficit or current account deficit. According to the research of Mulder & Braille (2001), the investment/GDP ratio, total export ratio, production growth rate, economic balance, historical restructuring level and inflation level are the key factors. In this study, 61 countries analyzed data from 25 developing countries (29 developed countries and 52 developing countries) estimated by Standard & Poor's and Moody's from 1992 to 1997. The study concluded that sovereign credit has six elements. These changes include GDP per capita, levels of external economic growth, underdevelopment rates, real growth rates and inflation. Roland (2004) estimated economic variables using the power method using data from 49 top developing countries. Second, Roland data, GDP per capita, GDP growth rate, inflation, debt ratio (debt/GDP and debt/export), debt repayment rate (debt/GDP), international reserves and economic openness (export/GDP), quality and reputation factors decide. Bisunodial-Venik (2005) analyzed the credit rating determinants of Moody's and Standard & Poor in 99 countries and found that current economic and financial indicators are insufficient to calculate the rating. He pointed out that the relationship between economic volatility and national credit levels differs at different levels. The author believes that this is not as important as countries that are financially stable and more volatile than countries in structural transition processes. Melius and Paget-Blank (200) analyze segmentation data for countries assessed by Standard & Poor's, Moody's and Fitch uses logistic and chain regression models. They conclude that the following six factors have the greatest impact on a country's credit rating: per capita income, government income, real exchange rate fluctuations, inflation, debt defaults and indicators of Afanso corruption; and Gomez Verrother (2011) ordered linear models and observations from 1995 to 2005 to analyze the short- and long-term determinants of the credit ratings of the three major credit rating agencies. They concluded that per capita GDP growth, GDP growth, government debt, and government balance will influence the short-term credit rating of government bonds. However, it will affect the influence of government, foreign debt, foreign currency assets

and long-term determinants. Erdem and Farley (2014) studied the effect of macroeconomic variables on domestic credit ratings in developing country markets. Budget / GDP equilibrium research finds that GDP per capita, government action, and important documents / GDP are the best reasons for national credit ratings, and chi Wa and Nasser (2015) analyze the national credit ratings of 53 countries from January 2000 to December 2011 have many variables. Macroeconomic and qualitative, such as historical basis, economic development and economic independence. They concluded that the impact of macroeconomic variables on a country's credit rating is similar to previous studies. It should also be emphasized that previous research has ignored independent economic variables that are critical to determining a country's credibility. In a study from 2002 to 2015, Reusenz and Krauks (201) compared key ranking factors. Before and after the European debt crisis in 2009, the sovereignty and demand probability models of 90 countries are needed. Studies have shown that since the European debt crisis, the importance of fiscal balance, economic development and foreign debt has greatly increased. In addition, research shows that in high-income countries, the importance of GDP growth is increasing, while in low-growth countries, government debt is even more important. Given the relevance of growing capital markets as a major source of investment for developing economies, the importance of rating agencies that provide standardized rating risk assessments in relation to increasing market investment continues to grow. In addition, the recent disclosure of the Basel Banking Supervision Committee in June 1999 highlights the functions of these institutions [Basel Banking Supervision Committee, 1999].

However, not all market participants are convinced that rating agencies are reliable enough to determine regulatory capital requirements. During the 1997/98 Asian disaster, the credit scores of many developing countries changed dramatically, raising questions about the accuracy and balance of the evaluation process [International Monetary Fund, 1999]. Although in the early days of the disaster, which began in July 1997, a large credit rating company accurately ruled out vulnerabilities within the financial structures of many Asian countries. But protection of investment ratings in many countries is equal to the disaster criteria and is clearly interpreted. With the help of many observers in the context of the Asian crisis, the suffix represents the cyclical and seasoned component of the global capital flow. The proxy action has been criticized for contributing to the sudden flow of capital following the catastrophe in Asia as a result of a pre-disaster grazing decline, a massive influx of capital. And moderate pressures on hobby rates are spreading [IMF, 1998].

2.1. What are the sovereign credit ratings

Like other credit ratings, a country rating is an examination of the relative likelihood of a debtor defaulting. The government usually has many traders, especially u. Buyers prefer securities with a higher rating than those without a clear credit risk rating. In the past, governments tended to classify bonds only in foreign currency, because bonds denominated in currencies were more likely to exist with global investors than services denominated in national currencies. In recent years, however, investors around the world have accelerated their call to issue bonds in currencies other than traditional international currencies, leading extra

countries to gain scores on domestic currency bonds as well. To date, however, the foreign credit ratings which are the focal point of this text remain hugely popular and influential on world bond markets. Sovereign scores are no longer important because some of the largest issuers on the international capital market are national governments, but also because this test affects the ratings assigned to borrowers of the same nationality. For example, companies rarely, if ever, assign credit score ratings to municipal neighborhoods, provincial authorities, or non-public business enterprises that are better than the company's home country.

2.3. Determinants of sovereign ratings

In Moody's Statement on Rating Standards, Moody's and Standard & Poor outlined several socioeconomic, political and political factors that form the basis of their sovereign credit rating (Moody's 1991; Moody's 1995; Standard & Poor's 1994). However, it is difficult to pinpoint a correlation between your criteria and actual scores, in part because not all criteria are quantifiable. In addition, the agency offers little guidance on the relative weights assigned to each factor. Even as a quantitative factor but it's hard to determine the relative weights that Moody's and Standard & Poor's set for, as agents rely heavily on standard debt. Which Factors Determine Sovereign Credit Ratings? A mortgage (government paid loan) can be a kind of business loan or long term loan. In particular, developed countries are major investors in capital markets. Also in the 1990s, the financing process for developing countries changed significantly as consolidation issues outpaced bank lending.

1. As a result the demand for sovereign credit ratings - the risk assessments assigned by credit rating agencies to government bonds - has significantly increased, all the more so as recent years have witnessed an important number of debt crises in developing countries.

2. Sovereign credit ratings significantly influence the terms and the extent to which, public and private lenders have access to international capital markets, particularly in developing countries. Deployment staff uses a combination of multiple variables and qualitative. (Economic, social and political) to allocate to debtors or debtors For this purpose, it is necessary to determine the maximum amount and to determine the level of national credit. This article attempts to answer this question.

3. The sovereign debt market, unlike the corporate debt market, is characterized by the absence of a bankruptcy code⁴. The collapse of the Russian GKO Union in August 1998 reflected this problem. Therefore, the reputation of the borrower does not depend on his talent. But it depends on your willingness to repay. (See, e.g., Eaton et al., 1986; Clark, 1997; and Clark and Zenaidi, 1999).

2.4. The Credit Ratings Of Moody's And Standars & Poor's

The country's repayment ability and willingness to classify Indeed, public debt is an assessment of the economic, monetary and political situation of an economy, taking into account the measure of national development. High debt default risk leads to lower credit ratings and higher government returns, which increases the cost of government financing to provide easy access to international capital markets. Governments that are reached by other issuers residing within the territory often require a rating. Rated securities are generally preferred over those not rated by many investors, especially in the United States. Sovereignty ratings are important because other issuers of the same nationality, private companies, local governments, and local governments seldom rank higher than their country of residence.

2.5. Sovereign ceiling and transfer risk

The sovereign ceiling may seem like a reasonable rule of thumb, as a first cut at determining the credit risk of a firm in an emerging market. Most companies are almost certainly riskier than their governments. However the rule itself only matters when it binds, and for companies whose ratings are constrained by the ceiling it has real effects. The investment policies of pension funds and insurance companies are tied to credit ratings, so that ratings determinants the pool of capital available to invest in a bond. Even apart from bond markets, investors' perception of country risk has important implications for every type of foreign investment in emerging markets. Decisions about bank loans, foreign direct investment, and portfolio investment in developing countries depend crucially on how investors perceive the risks associated with the home country of the borrower or project. The sovereign ceiling rule is related to the common practice of using sovereign spreads to impute the country risk associated with projects undertaken in emerging markets. One popular way to incorporate country risk is to add a risk premium related to the sovereign spread on to the cost of capital, under the argument that sovereign yield spread proxies 2 for the firm's country-related default risk. According to a survey conducted by Keck, Levensgood and Longfield (1998), many practitioners add risk premiums into the discount rates to adjust for country risk. Once the sovereign ceiling rule was abolished, the spreads for the affected firms in Argentina narrowed by 30-50 basis points. If the sovereign ceiling affects the practitioners' adjustment of cost of capital in emerging market projects by 50 basis points, then it constitutes an economically significant constraint to emerging market investment. The method of accounting for country risk can thus have a big impact on what projects are undertaken in emerging markets. Broadly speaking, there are two justifications for the sovereign ceiling. One is simply that a firm and its government operate in the same macroeconomic environment. An economy-wide downturn may lower the firm's prospects at the same time that it increases the likelihood of a government repayment crisis. Likewise, a currency devaluation will imply difficulties for both the firms and the government in meeting foreign currency obligations. A more direct explanation is that a country's government has the power to tax firms, impose foreign exchange controls, or seize the firm's assets. If the government's repayment capacity falls, the government is more likely to exercise one or more of these rights, which in turn will lower the firm's repayment capacity. We refer to this effect as "transfer risk," that is, the risk that a sovereign borrower's repayment problems will be transferred to the firm.

3 Transfer risk arising from the possibility of currency controls is the main justification credit rating agencies use for the sovereign ceiling. Euromoney (1997) cites a senior analyst at Moody's: "From our standpoint, it's inevitable that controls would be imposed on private companies" when a government defaults on its debt, while S&P argued that this would be less likely in a dollarized economy.

3. Materials and methods

This section describes the data structure and analysis used in the analysis. In this case, the data collection process for the variables is explained first, and then the data analysis process is determined. Data and modeling:

3.2. Data and model

In terms of the degrees used in this study, where most of the previous studies focused on two senior ranks, Standard and Poor's and Moody's, this study extends to earlier publications by applying royalties awarded by Fitch. The increase in interest rates includes a number of factors, which reflect the political and economic threats of each country. The economic crisis speaks volumes about the government's ability to repay its work on time and says it will be determined by binary and regulatory bodies such as regulatory bodies, where political threats remain. speaks of the king's willingness to pay his debt. So far, every company offers research and credit ideas in more than 90 countries and submits notifications for foreign and domestic loans by major governments. However, the list of countries under consideration is not the same for every company and in the case of Fitch Ratings, the current ratings are for about 80 countries. Some of these standards are not counted. Similarly, companies that consider the status quo provide a small guide for the load assigned to each change, and the company is based on this type of standard, which is not easily available. Second, choose climate change to measure how well each country gets data. The World Bank's database ensures economic transformation. The relationship between the variables is considered to be able to determine the identity of the landlord and the national authority, and its willingness to pay is detailed as follows:

- GDP: GDP and consumer prices are in the interests of manufacturers and the economy in addition to tariffs and other contributions that are not invested in the value of this product. Higher economic conditions indicate that over time a country's debt will be more easily repaid.
- Inflation: Customer price comparison reflects the rate of change in the price of the quantity of goods and services that customers regularly purchase. Long-term growth that increases peoples satisfaction to influence the political and economic situation of the country.
- Panel data: Panel data (also known as linear time series or segment data) is a set of data that observes the behavior of an object over time. Panel data allows you to control variables that cannot be observed or measured, such as differences in cultural factors or business practices across the enterprise or constantly changing variables. But in essence (e.g. national policy, federal regulations, international agreements, etc.).

- Current account: A large current account deficit implies the dependence of a country on foreign creditors. A persistent deficit affects the country's sustainability.
- Foreign debt/GDP: This ratio is negatively related to default risk.
- Real exchange rate: The real exchange rate assesses the trade competitiveness of the economy.
- Default history: A country's default history affects its reputation.
- Ratio debt/GDP: The higher this ratio is, the greater the occurrence of a liquidity crisis.
- Ratio reserves/imports: The higher this ratio is, the more reserves are available to service foreign debt.
- Ratio investment/GDP: This ratio captures the future growth ability of a country and it is a decreasing function of default.
- Corruption Index: This index is a measure of political risk and can reduce a country's willingness to pay.
- Regulatory quality, accountability, rule of law and political stability: These indicators provide a means of evaluating the governance of a country and affect a country's willingness to pay.

This explains the differences individually. In this study, the relationship between the highest credit rates determined by credit institutions and macroeconomic investors was examined. The aim of this study is to create a new ranking system and to give credit to the 23 countries of the rich and poor that depend on developing countries. Some economic methods are used to rank, and at the end we evaluate positive and negative results on a negative level based on the evidence in the available documents, a change that can define the level. Government levels are described as follows: Real GDP Growth (G), GDP Per Capita (GPC), Inflation (CPI), Budget / GDP (BD) Balance, Investment / GDP In this study, we developed a survey which he received. Receiving a change of law is a mark of a member of a national party.

3.3.Explanatory Variables

Table 1: Explanatory Variables

Variable	Explanation	Source
Real GDP growth	Real per capita	Global Finance, World Bank
Unemployment	Unemployment (% of total labor Force)	IMF
Investment GDP	Is the measure of physical investment	World Bank
External balance	Average annual current account surplus relative	World bank and OECD national data
Export GDP	Country exports good	World Bank
External debt.	Foreign currency debt relative	Global Finance
Nominal GDP	Gross domestic product using current price	Global Finance
Inflation	Consumer Price (annual %)	Statista
Budget Balance	Central Government Debt, Total (%of GDP)	IMF

In a study analyzing the sovereign credit rating and seven variables described for 2011-2020, the unemployment data that determines the actual GDP per capita budget was obtained from the Wikipedia database while the data belonging to the GDP variable. Real GDP, Investment GDP, Exports are compiled from World Bank database. And the rest of the real GDP inflation data is collected from Global Finance and Statista. Eviews 8 and Excel are also used for the analysis.

3.4. Panel data analysis

Panel data econometric techniques are used in this study

S&P	AAA	AA+	AA	AA-	A+		CCC	CCC-	CC	D
Fitch	AAA	AA+	AA	AA-	A+		CCC	CCC-	CC	D

Table 2. Linear Transformations Table

¹ Austria, Finland, Denmark, Germany, Netherlands, Norway, Sweden, Switzerland, Belgium, France, Ireland, Norway, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, United Kingdom, Luxemburg, Lithonia, Uruguay, Oman, Portugal

² Bangladesh, India, Pakistan, Kazakhstan, Afghanistan, Sri-Lanka

Moody's	Aaa	Aa1	Aa2	Aa3	A1		Caa2	Caa3	Ca	C
	<u>23</u>	<u>22</u>	21	<u>20</u>	<u>19</u>		<u>4</u>	<u>3</u>	<u>2</u>	<u>1</u>

Source: Afonso, Gomes & Rother, 2007:34

Credit grades in the study are analyzed by transforming according to this scale which is also used in many studies in the literature. The credit rating of each country is based on the sovereign credit rating at the end of the year (excluding positive or negative outlook). As a novelty, we specify the explanatory variables by using a factor analysis technique. Therefore, the initial step is the implementation of this factor analysis. Factor analysis seeks to discover if the observed variables can be explained largely or entirely in terms of a much smaller number of variables which are called factors. Factor analysis provides us an empirical basis in creating fewer but independent variables out of many highly correlated variables. Another advantage of using this method is in resolving the problem of linear differences between the specified values due to unrelated factors, whereas the variables applied to these elements are not. The results of the factor analysis provided us with six homogenous factor groups reduced from 8 variables². When these tasks are done, the command to approach is what separates the bad site into an example. When these tasks are done, the command to approach is what separates the bad site into an example. Prob is the probability that the variable distribution is modified to a useful value. An ordered probit model is:

$$y^* = x'_{it}\beta + \gamma Z + \varepsilon$$

where y^* is an unobservable latent variable that measures the credit worthiness of a country in period t . x_{it} is a vector of time varying explanatory variables and β is a vector of unknown parameters. Z contains time invariant regressors that are generally dummy variables and ε_{it} is a random disturbance term. If the distribution of ε_{it} is chosen to be normal, then ultimately this produces an ordered probit model. As usual, y_{it}^* is unobserved. What we assume here is that y_{it}^* is related to the observed variable y_{it} , which is the Standard and poor rating in this case, in the following way:

$$\begin{aligned}
 y_i &= 0 \text{ if } y_i^* < \tau_0 \\
 &1 \text{ if } \tau_0 < y_i^* < \tau_1 \\
 &2 \text{ if } \tau_1 < y_i^* < \tau_2 \\
 &3 \text{ if } \tau_2 < y_i^* < \tau_3 \\
 &4 \text{ if } \tau_3 < y_i^* < \tau_4 \\
 &5 \text{ if } \tau_4 < y_i^* < \tau_5 \\
 &\dots \\
 &23 \text{ if } \tau_{22} < y_i^* < \tau_{23}
 \end{aligned}$$

where they $\tau_s (\tau_0 < \tau_1 < \tau_2 < \dots < \tau_{23})$ are known threshold parameters to be estimated. The following model may be named as factor ordered probit model, where y^* is an unobservable latent variable that measures the credit-worthiness of a country in period t . F_{it} is a vector of factors derived from factor analysis and θ is a vector of unknown parameters. Z_{it} contains time invariant regressors that are generally dummy variables and ε_{it} is a random disturbance term.

$$y_{it}^* = F_{it}'\beta + \gamma Z_{it} + \delta(F * Z)_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Regarding a rating schedule, estimation results will be expressed in a 1-24 point scale, and then we perform a linear transformation to the letter grades assigned by STANDARD AND POOR.

¹ Austria, Finland, Denmark, Germany, Netherlands, Norway, Sweden, Switzerland, Belgium, France, Ireland, Norway, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, United Kingdom, Luxemburg, Lithuania, Uruguay, Oman, Portugal

² Bangladesh, India, Pakistan, Kazakhstan, Afghanistan, Sri-Lanka

3.5. Results and discussion

In this part of study, it is useful to provide information on the frequency of sovereign credit ratings before this assessment. Table 3, prepared for this purpose, shows the frequency distributions of sovereign credit ratings of the countries rated by the S & P and subject to the analysis.

	rating	Frequency	Cumulative %
1	AA+	2	10.53%
2	AA	3	26.32%
3	AAA	6	57.89%
4	AA-	2	68.42%
5	A-	1	73.68%
6	A	1	78.95%
7	BB-	1	84.21%
8	CCC+	1	89.47%
9	B-	1	94.74%
10	BBB-	1	100.00%
	Total	19	100.00%

3.6. Frequency

Table 3. Frequency

Firstly, as can be seen in table 3, there are a total of 280 observations covering the ten-year period of 60 low and high-income countries. Also, it is seen that a significant part of the ratings is accumulated in BB-, CCC+, B-, BBB- for low-income countries. And the cumulative percentage at BB- is 84.21%. In other words, a considerable number of low-income countries have not reached the investment grade level BBB- and above BBB-. For the group of high-income countries, the first thing to notice is that credit ratings at AAA level have a significant share in total frequencies. Within a total of 280 observations of 23 countries, AAA is in the first place with 159 observations. The percentage of AAA that represents the lowest risk level is 57.89 %. This shows how effective the level of economic development is in assessing the

Table 3 also shows frequency distributions for credit ratings for all countries in the study. As you can see, the AAA credit rating has the highest percentage for the 105 countries analyzed. Also, you can see that, the AAA credit rating constitutes approximately 16% of the total frequencies with 159 observations. This shows that the sovereign credit ratings of high-income countries rated by S & P are stable at high levels for many years, unlike the countries in the low-income groups.

As can be seen from Table 3, another credit rating level, which has a large number of observations, is the AA level. When the frequencies of this rating level are examined, it is seen that the total number of observations of AA is in the second place after AAA. This credit level has about 10% of the total observations with 95 observations.

On the other hand, frequency percentages of other credit ratings have more homogeneous distribution. Another important point that should be mentioned for all countries is related to the cumulative percentages of frequency distributions. Cumulative percentages of credit ratings below the CCC+ level is too low to be ignored. After discussing the frequency of credit spreads in this study, there was a correlation between rate of change and rule / test scores and the results of the plan were individually reviewed. It is helpful to investigate the relationship between the variables described in this form prior to the policy review / in project outcomes. Table 4 provided here is a positive correlation between the study variables as seen in the table 4, for each country. Therefore, there is no objection to using the data of these variables in the analysis.

3.7. Correlation matrix of explanatory variables

Table 4. Correlation Matrix of Explanatory Variables

	Investm. GDP %	Unemploy.	OECD national data	Real GDP Growth%	Export GDP%	Inflation	Budget Balance	external debt (\$ million)
Investm. GDP %	1.00000							
Unemploy.	0.06962	1.00000						
External balance data	0.09635	-0.27954	1.00000					
Real GDP Growth%	0.02993	-0.13047	0.54899	1.00000				
Export GDP%	0.12323	-0.33308	0.76637	0.66327	1.00000			
Inflation	-0.30122	-0.46495	-0.17914	-0.00195	-0.03955	1.00000		
Budget Balance	0.33566	-0.43053	0.22257	0.05080	0.00233	0.37212	1.00000	
external debt (\$ million)	-0.35171	0.13268	-0.22028	-0.06327	-0.24628	0.06098	-0.08333	1.00000

High-income countries & Low-income countries

	Investm. GDP %	Unemploy.	OECD national data	Real GDP Growth%	Export GDP%	Inflation	Budget Balance	external debt (\$ million)
Investm. GDP %	1.00000							
Unemploy.	-0.33598	1.00000						
OECD national data	0.42202	0.68522	1.00000					
Real GDP Growth%	0.86165	-0.48182	0.24788	1.00000				
Export GDP%	0.72730	-0.29485	0.26356	0.38946	1.00000			
Inflation	0.24723	-0.67186	-0.28104	0.60080	0.12143	1.00000		
Budget Balance	0.42501	-0.95829	-0.53328	0.54368	0.46766	0.77504	1.00000	
external debt (\$ million)	1.00000	1.00000	1.00000	1.00000	-1.00000	1.00000	-1.00000	1.00000

4. Conclusion

Numerous studies have attempted to determine what to do in the industry and in the countryside (see, for example, Ederington and Yawitz 1987; Moon and Stotsky 1993), but this study has identified regulators such as Moody's, Standard & Poor's, and Poole decided. This is the first study to determine content. The king's first risk analysts discuss other risk indicators or do a risk assessment for a credit rating. For example, Feder and Uy (1985) and Lee (1993) examined the level of ownership status by examining foreign banks declaring "companies" every six months. Taylor (1995) discussed the importance of some of the changes we have studied, but did not try to look at the descriptions of individuals. The independence of capital arising from globalization has created a new passion for "corporate". The World Credit Ratings Agency (CCR) has achieved this goal. In addition, the credit rating of credit card companies has become an integral part of the current economy. ISSN 2219-1933 (Print), 2219-6021 (Online) Immigration Research Center. www.ijbssnet.com 125 in this context, this research focuses on local authority credit levels and studies macroeconomic transformation and processing. Assume that not all countries are assessed according to the same standards. When compared, the countries studied are grouped and analyzed within 3 countries according to the macroeconomics used in this study, having a significant impact on the degree of ownership of Land owners, except for the same type of unemployment in low and middle income countries. In countries with large economies, this vital relationship is essential to transforming everyone's income, inflation, unemployment and government debt. These results provide macroeconomic value and lead to countries seeking to improve their credit rating. Finally, it can be said that capital expenditure, growth, budget and government debt are important factors for credit in any country. However, there were many conflicts between the plans. In other words, household income level, general interest rate, and utility bills play an important role in national investment. In other words, countries that want to attract capital must implement economic policies that affect these economic changes. For this reason, it can be said that economic factors, especially economic reformers, are necessary to determine the credibility of a country. But the impact of politics and the understanding of a nation is very important. This white paper examines the characteristics of home credit in the eurozone countries. Available books provide mixed results that point to a higher level of complexity.

To trade with this issue, we used the Bayesian access method to include data collection from countries in the region of 22 euros from 2011 to 2020. It also tested the debt crisis that began in 20011. Morality? Our clear evidence shows that before the crisis, change rates and also GDP were the only important factors determining national level. But after the crisis, GDP growth, debt-to-income, personal debt, and external debt. To have a significant impact on rankings, these results reflect the uncertainty of the branding industry and convince critics to focus on the inaccuracies of the credit industry. It is also believed that the reason the credit bureau could not report the turmoil at the time was due to the process for selecting the appropriate amount for the factors that determine the level of government.

5. References

- Afonso, A. (2002). Understanding the determinants of government debt rating: evidence for the two leading agencies. Department of Economics And Research Center On The Portuguese Economy (CISEP), Lisbon
- Afonso, A., Gomes, P. & Rother, P. (2007). What hides behind sovereign debt ratings?, European Central Bank Working Paper Series, No:711
- Afonso, A., Gomes, P. & Rother, P. (2011). Short and long-run determinants of sovereign debt credit ratings. *International Journal of Finance and Economics*, 16 (19), 115
- Alsakka, R. & Gwilym, O. (2010). Leads and lags in sovereign credit ratings. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 34, 2614-2626
- Baltagi, B. H. (2008). *Econometrics*. Germany: Springer
- Bissoondoyal-Bheenick, E. (2005). An analysis of the determinants of sovereign ratings. *Global Finance Journal*, 15, 251-280
- Cantor, R. & Packer, F. (1996). Determinants of impact of sovereign credit. *FRNBY Economic Policy Review*, 2, 37-53
- Chee, S.W., Fah, C.F. & Nassir, A.M. (2015). Macroeconomics determinants of sovereign credit ratings. *International Business Research*, 8(2), 42
- Erdem, O & Varli, Y. (2014). Understanding the sovereign credit rating of emerging markets. *Emerging Market Review*, 20, 42-57
- Greene, W.H. (2003). *Econometric Analysis*. New Jersey: Pearson Education
- Mellios, C. & Paget-Blanc, E. (2006). Which factors determine sovereign credit ratings?. *The European Journal of Finance*, 12 (4), 361-377
- Mulder, C. & Perrelli, R. (2001). Foreign credit ratings for emerging market economies. IMF Working Paper No:191
- Reusens, P. & Croux, C. (2017). Sovereign credit rating determinants: A comparison before and after the European debt crisis. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 77, 108-121
- Rowland, P. (2004). Determinants of spread, credit ratings and creditworthiness for emerging market sovereign debt: a followup study using pooled data analysis. Banco de la Republica de Colombia, Borradores de Economia, 295
- Schroeter, U. G. (2013). *Handbook of Key Global Financial Markets, Institutions, and Infrastructure*. 37390
- Wooldridge, J.M. (2002). *Econometric analysis of cross section and panel data*. London: MIT Press

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

